
CSCCE Tech Case Study: Using GitHub to manage session proposals for CarpentryCon

About this case study

In 2023, CSCCE hosted a series of community “Tools Trials” that focused on tools commonly used for community management in open-source and open-source-supporting communities. The goal of the series - which consisted of several live webinars with Q&A and this accompanying tip sheet collection - was to share existing knowledge and provide any scientific community manager with options about tools and use cases they could explore further.

One of the most commonly used tools by these communities is GitHub. In this case study, we summarize how The Carpentries uses GitHub to organize their flagship conference, CarpentryCon.

What is GitHub?

[GitHub](#) is a version control platform for storing, collaborating on, and tracking projects. It is primarily used for software development, but can also be used for other collaborative work. It utilizes [Git](#), which is an open-source version control system that can track which users make changes to computer files (e.g., code, documents) and when. Although there are other software platforms that use Git, GitHub is the most popular. [Check out our introductory tip sheet for more information.](#)

Overview of The Carpentries and CarpentryCon

[The Carpentries](#) is a global community focused on teaching software and data skills via three lesson programs: Data Carpentry, Library Carpentry, and Software Carpentry. To date, their community of more than 2200 instructors has delivered more than 4000 workshops using open-source lessons, which means that they are freely available, community-maintained, and licensed CC BY.

The Carpentries community includes numerous community roles, including (but not limited to) lesson maintainers, instructors, instructor trainers, curriculum advisors, community coordinators, and a core team. Members convene in many ways, including around a specific topic or project, through community calls, and in regional and whole-community meetings like CarpentryCon. CarpentryCon is a semi-regular gathering of members of The Carpentries community who are interested in upskilling to support a range of community activities. The event has taken place both in-person and online.

The Carpentries uses GitHub to support CarpentryCon in two ways: as the underlying infrastructure for their conference website, and for managing conference proposal submissions from members interested in contributing a session to the event. In this case study, we will focus on this second use

case. For more on using GitHub as a collaborative underpinning of a static website, [check out this separate case study](#), which was also part of our Tools Trials series.

Using GitHub to manage conference proposal submissions

The process for submitting a proposal to CarpentryCon relies on submitting issues to the [CarpentryCon repo](#) to propose a session. Issue templates are used to standardize submissions and ask for the following information:

- The title of the proposed session
- Logistical details about the session such as permission to record it and the session type
- An abstract
- Information about the person submitting the proposal
- A space to indicate a request for community involvement

Figure 1 provides an example:

BinxiePeterson commented on Jun 11, 2020 · edited

Title of the session: How to prevent and kick burnout to the curb

Session details

- Session type: Breakout discussion
- Keywords: burnout, stress, stress management, relaxation, efficiency
- Permission to record this session: Yes

Abstract

Since becoming part of the Carpentries' community, I can't imagine what my life was like before. I have learned so many things in the past few year, even though it was a long, hard road and many lessons were learned. Burnout was a reality for me, and I am certain that it is for many others as well. I would thus like to propose a breakout session where people can share their experiences, challenges, and solutions to preventing/treating burnout. We not only want an active community, but a healthy one.

Personal details

- Name or pseudo name of the session lead: Bianca Peterson
- Co-leads' names (we recommend involving 2 helpers/co-leads): Toby Hodges
- Email or other ways to contact the session leads/co-leads: bianca.peterson777@gmail.com
- Country of residence and/or compatible Time Zones (provide options): South Africa (GMT+2)
- Would you like to present this multiple times, in other time zones: Yes (Eastern Time)
- Would you like to volunteer to be listed as a wrangler/host for your time zone: No

Is there any help you would like to invite from the community? Please provide below in bullet points.

- I would like to invite people from anywhere in the world to lead / speak at this session.
- Motivational speakers are welcome.
- Other comments: I don't have any qualifications/certifications regarding treating burnout. I merely want to share my experience and hope that others will share their experiences too. In that way, people will realize that this is nothing to be ashamed of and that things can get better.

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Figure 1

An example of a completed issue containing details about a session proposal for CarpentryCon. This is a customized issue template to gather the same types of information from all session proposers.

Figure 2

The list of issues in the CarpentryCon submission repo. Each issue represents a unique session proposal. Labels are used to indicate location (dark blue), stage of the planning process (lavender) and session type (orange). On the right, the headshots of contributors and the number of comments on each issue are displayed.

Once the user submits their issue to the repo (Figure 2), other members of the community can then ask questions or indicate their interest in the session using the chat feature, as well as by adding emojis (e.g., a thumbs up). An example can be found in Figure 3.

Figure 3

Example of comments associated with a proposal submission ([view the submission in GitHub](#)). Comments are threaded, include the option of adding emoji reactions, and indicate where the author of the issue joins the conversation.

Using GitHub to refine the conference program

After the proposal window closes, conference organizers then use additional features in GitHub to refine the conference program. Labels are used to categorize different session types, the planning stage of each submission, and the location of the session. Issues allow conversations to be cross-referenced ([example](#)) and the chat feature provides a direct way of connecting with session organizers. Refer back to Figure 1 to see how this looks in the list view of issues.

Pros and cons of using GitHub for this use case

[For general pros and cons of using GitHub for community management, [please refer to our overview tip sheet.](#)]

Pros:

- Threaded comments allow community members, not just members of the planning and/or selection committees, to comment on and discuss proposal submissions.
- Customized issue templates standardize the submission process.
- Labels give organizers the ability to add metadata to proposals.
- Transparency to the proposal submission and review process as anyone can read and follow the process (with or without a GitHub account).

Cons:

- Requires some level of comfort using the platform. Someone without a profile or unfamiliar with the platform may not feel included to participate.
- Actions displayed in issues disrupt the conversation thread, which could make it difficult for some viewers to follow the conversation for that issue.

Both of these cons could potentially be mitigated by offering programming or resources to support use of the platform.

Additional resources

- [Maneesha Sane's full presentation on GitHub for CarpentryCon](#) - Watch this case study being presented during CSCCE's Tools Trial in this short video
- Creating [issue templates](#)
- Level up your [issue templates](#) with forms
- The Carpentries templates:
 - https://github.com/carpentries-incubator/proposals/blob/main/.github/ISSUE_TEMPLATE/lesson_proposal.yml?plain=1
 - https://github.com/carpentries-incubator/proposals/blob/main/.github/ISSUE_TEMPLATE/lesson_proposal.yml
 - https://github.com/swcarpentry/.github/tree/main/.github/ISSUE_TEMPLATE

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MANEESHA SANE - Writing - Reviewing and Editing

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